

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF MILITARY IMAGES IN HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: Today, in our country, the great work towards building an independent legal democratic state and a free civil society creates new conditions for the realization of opportunities for self-realization and spiritual, intellectual and practical development. This, in turn, requires a new attitude and approach to the spiritual wealth created by mankind. At the same time, we will briefly consider the psychological features of the formation of military imaginations of students studying in the upper grades of our country.

Keywords: Optimism, Appreciation, Skills and support, Motivation for creativity, Concepts and emotions

The main part: Developmental psychology is a science of mental development of people of different ages, mental characteristics, criteria and mechanisms of their specific factors. He also studies the characteristics of people of a certain age. Therefore, developmental psychology has a special place in social life in education, groups and communities, production and family relations. The problem of the formation of the human personality and the development of cognitive processes cannot be rationally solved without taking into account the laws of the development of the human psyche. Therefore, the issue of "human factor" has become a topical issue.

The psychological characteristics of the formation of military ideas among high school students may depend on the age of the students, the level of spiritual and intellectual development, and the external and internal conditions of the educational process. This process is related to self-mastery of students, development of creative and analytical thoughts, striving to find solutions to problems, creating creative works and enabling them to be realized.

The following psychological characteristics are important in the formation of military visions:

✚ Perspective: It is necessary to create an opportunity for self-expression of perspective and independence in the formation of military imaginations.

✚ Rewarding: It is important to reward students, encourage them and support them in their learning rather than criticizing their achievements.

✚ Skills and Support: It is psychologically important to value students' skills, support them, and not help them develop their military imaginations, and support their feedback.

✚ Encouraging creative activity: Encouraging students to engage in creative activity, empowering them to pursue innovations and express their thoughts is important in forming military imaginations.

✚ Concepts and Emotions: Developing students' concepts is essential in helping them express their thoughts and build their military imaginations.

Knowing the factors and conditions that have a positive effect on the development and change of the psyche of people of different ages and sexes, the moral and physical maturity of all nations and peoples living in our country, and the effective use of them has finally become necessary.

Conclusion: These psychological characteristics are important in the development of students' military imagination and can help them in the process of self-mastery.

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